

**IMPACT OF HOME ENVIRONMENT ON THE ADJUSTMENT OF SECONDARY
SCHOOL STUDENTS**

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Abstract

The study focused on home environment and its impact on the adjustment of secondary school students. Present study was conducted on 200 rural and urban students of class 10th of four schools of Tarn Taran city. Data was analysed by using 't-test' and 2 way ANOVA. Results showed that urban secondary school students have better home environment and they have better adjustment as compared to their counterparts. Moreover, findings of the research reveals that boys and girls of urban areas have the same home environment and therefore both of them have same adjustment patterns but girls of rural areas got better home environment so they are better adjusted as compared to the boys of rural areas. Further 2-way ANOVA results also shows that there is significant interactional effect of home environment and locality on adjustments of secondary school students but this interaction of home environment and gender on adjustment of secondary school students is not significant.

Introduction

Psychoanalysts stressed the importance of early home experiences in the development of child's behaviour and attitudes. Home sets the pattern for child's attitude towards people, things and instructions. Home is the first agency where the child gets education in sociability. Home environment is the aggregate of all those physical and psychological conditions that determine the growth and development of the child. The environment created at home accelerates or retards the development of the child. It affects the child at home, in society and in social groups.

It is a primary socialization unit and is, therefore considered to be a very important factor influencing the development of a child. Home is the mean that links child and society and mirror the norms of a particular class. Through the family, a child is introduced to his culture and gains competence in living with its normative restrictions. The patterns of interaction and behaviour of the family members play a vital role in the behaviour and adjustment patterns of the individual. Basic adjustment begin from home right from childhood and it can be learned only where there is adequate support, love and affection from the family. Family cohesion and supportive relationship between family members are associated with adolescent psychological adaptation and lower depression. Whereas families with psychological distress and aggressive behaviour find disorders.

Many research studies showed that adolescents who are grown with support and care of the family members, are better adjusted than those who are from dissociative families, still there is some set back in the behaviour of rural and urban students and boys and girls of secondary schools. So, the present study, attempts to find out the impact of home environment on the adjustment of secondary school students in relation to their locale and gender.

Objectives

- To study the impact of home environment on the adjustment of secondary school students.
- To study the adjustment of secondary school students in relation to their locale.
- To study the home environment of secondary school students in relation to their locale.
- To compare the home environment of secondary school boys and girls of rural area.
- To compare the home environment of secondary school boys and girls of urban area.
- To compare the adjustment of secondary school boys and girls of rural area.
- To compare the adjustment of secondary school boys and girls of urban area.
- To study the interaction effect of home environment and locale on the adjustment of secondary school students.
- To study the interaction effect of home environment and gender on the adjustment of secondary school students.

Hypotheses

- There is no significant difference in adjustment of rural and urban secondary school students.
- There is no significant difference in home environment of rural and urban secondary school students.
- There is no significant difference in home environment of boys and girls students of urban area.
- There is no significant difference in home environment of boys and girls students of rural area.
- There is no significant difference in adjustment of boys and girls students of urban area.
- There is no significant difference in adjustment of boys and girls students of rural area.
- There is no significant interactional effect of home environment and locale on the adjustment of secondary school students.
- There is no significant interactional effect of home environment and gender on the adjustment of secondary school students.

Delimitations Of The Problem

The present study is delimited to private and government secondary schools of Tarn Taran only.

Research Methodology

The present study comes under the domain of descriptive research.

Sample

A sample of 200 students studying in 10th class was drawn from different schools of Tarn Taran district.

Research Tools

The following tools were used to collect the data

- Home environment Inventory by Karuna Shankar Mishra (1989)
- Adjustment inventory by Mittal (1965).

Statistical Techniques

Statistical techniques like mean, S.D., t-test and ANOVA were used for the analysis of data.

In order to find out the interaction of home environment and gender , home environment and locale on the adjustment of secondary school students , 2*2 factorial design high and low home environment were framed .

1. Home environment * gender
2. Home environment * locale

Since the number of cases in different cells of factorial designs varied in different combinations , it was thought desirable to have equal number of cases in each cell, with varying number in each factorial design (depending upon availability of minimum number of cases in each cell in a particular design.) The analysis of variance with n= 10 in each cell were carried out in home environment * gender , home environment * locale , factorial designs . Needless to mention , it is an essential 10, requirement to have equal number of cases in each cell for applying analysis of variance to have valid results.

Analysis and Interpretation of data

Hypothesis-I

There is no significant difference in adjustment of rural and urban secondary school students

The value of means, standard deviations and t-value of adjustment of rural and urban secondary school students are shown in table 1.1

Table No. 1.1

N, Mean, Standard Deviation, t-value of scores of adjustment of rural and urban secondary school students

Area	Sample (N)	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (σ)	(t-value)
Urban	100	200.9	27.6	4.88**
Rural	100	179.1	35.3	

** Significant at level 0.05

The results in table 1.1 clearly show that the t- value for adjustment of rural and urban secondary school students came out to be 4.88 which is significant at 0.05 level. This higher significant value indicates that urban and rural students differ in their scores of adjustment. The high mean score in favour of urban reveals that urban in the present sample have a better adjustment in comparison with rural students.

Thus the hypothesis that “*There is no significant difference in adjustment of rural and urban secondary school students*” was rejected leading to the conclusion that urban secondary school students are more adjusted as compared to their counterparts.

Hypothesis-II

There is no significant difference in home environment of rural and urban secondary school students

The value of the Mean, Standard Deviation and t-value of the home environment of rural and urban secondary school students are shown in table 1.2.

Table 1.2

N, Mean, Standard Deviation and t-value of scores of home environment of rural and urban secondary school students

Area	Sample (N)	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (σ)	(t-value)
Urban	100	220.9	11.75	3.94**
Rural	100	214.4	11.56	

** Significant at level 0.05.

The results in table 4.2 clearly shows that the t-value for home environment of rural and urban secondary school students came out to be 3.94 which is significant at 0.05 level. This higher significant value indicates that urban and rural students differ in their scores of home environment. The high mean score in favour of urban students reveals that urban students in the present sample have a better home environment in comparison with rural students.

Thus the hypothesis that “*there is no significant difference in home environment of rural and urban secondary school students*” was rejected leading to the conclusion that urban secondary students have better home environment as compared to their counterparts.

Hypothesis-III

There is no significant difference in home environment of boys and girls students of urban area

Table 1.3

N, Mean, Standard Deviation and t-value of scores of home environment of boys and girls of urban secondary schools

Gender	Sample (N)	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (σ)	(t-value)
Boys	50	220.6	13.1	0.30*
Girls	50	221.4	13.2	

* Insignificant at level 0.05.

Table 1.3 referring to the third hypothesis shows that t-value for the boys and girls of urban area for the variable of home environment is 0.30 which is insignificant at level 0.05. This means that boys and girls students of urban area taken up for present study do not differ in the variable of home environment. Thus the hypothesis that “*there is no significant difference in home environment of boys and girls students of urban area*” was accepted leading to the conclusion that the boys and girls of urban area have the same home environment.

Hypothesis-Iv

There is no significant difference in home environment of boys and girls students of rural area

Table 1.4

N, Mean, Standard Deviation and t-value of scores of home environment of boys and girls of rural secondary schools

Gender	Sample (N)	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (σ)	(t-value)
Boys	50	212.8	10.5	3.25**
Girls	50	220.2	12.2	

** Significant at level 0.05.

Table 1.4 referring to the fourth hypothesis shows that t-value for the boys and girls of rural area for the variable of home environment is 0.30 which is significant at level 0.05. This means that boys and girls students of rural area taken up here differ in the variable of home environment. Thus the hypothesis that “*there is no significant difference in home environment of boys and girls students of rural area*” is rejected leading to the conclusion that girls have better home environment than boys of rural area.

Hypothesis-V

There is no significant difference in adjustment of boys and girls students of urban area

The value of means, standard deviations and t-value of adjustment of boys and girls of secondary school students are shown in table 1.5

Table 1.5

N, Mean, Standard Deviation, t-value of scores of adjustment of boys and girls of secondary school students of urban area

Gender	Sample (N)	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (σ)	(t-value)
Boys	50	207.6	27.6	0.02*
Girls	50	207.8	50.7	

* Insignificant at level 0.05

The results in table 1.5 clearly shows that the t-value for adjustment of boys and girls of secondary school students came out to be 0.02 which is not significant at 0.05 level. This highly significant value indicates that boys and girls that have been taken up statistically not differ in their scores of adjustment.

Thus the hypothesis that “*there is no significant difference in adjustment of boys and girls of urban area*” is accepted leading to the conclusion that there does not exist significant difference in the adjustment of boys and girls of secondary school students of urban area.

Hypothesis-Vi

There is no significant difference in adjustment of boys and girls students of rural area

The value of means, standard deviations and t-value of adjustment of boys and girls of secondary school students of rural area are shown in table 1.6

Table 1.6

N, Mean, Standard Deviation, t-value of scores of adjustment of boys and girls of secondary school students of rural area

Gender	Sample (N)	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (σ)	t-value
Boys	50	172.6	37.6	2.41**
Girls	50	195.2	54.5	

** Significant at level 0.05

The results in table 1.6 clearly shows that the t-value for adjustment of boys and girls of secondary schools came out to be 2.41 which is significant at 0.05 level. This highly significant value indicates that boys and girls that have been taken up statistically differ in their scores of adjustment. The higher mean score in favour of girls reveals that girls in the present sample have a better adjustment in comparison with boys of rural area.

Thus the hypothesis that “*there is no significant difference in adjustment of boys and girls of rural area*” is rejected leading to the conclusion that girl students of rural area are more adjusted as compared to the boys.

Hypothesis-VII

There is no significant interactional effect of home environment and locale on the adjustment of secondary school students

Table 1.7
Summary of analysis of variance
(Home environment x Locale) : Adjustment

Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	F Value
Home Environment (A)	1	57.6	57.6	0.48*
Locale (B)	1	4.9	4.9	0.04*
Interaction (Ax B)	1	624.5	624.5	5.24**
Within	36	4290.48	119.18	-

* Insignificant at level 0.05.

The results in table 1.7 clearly shows that f-value for interactional effect of home environment and Locale came out to be 5.24 which is significant at 0.05 level. The results shows that Interactional effects of home environment across both rural and urban areas of locality on adjustment of secondary school students is significant.

Hypothesis-VIII

There is no significant interactional effect of home environment and gender on the adjustment of secondary school students

Table 1.8

Summary of analysis of variance
(Home environment x Gender) : Adjustment

Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	F Value
Home Environment (A)	1	57.6	57.6	0.06*
Gender (B)	1	562.5	562.5	0.57*
Interaction (Ax B)	1	688.9	688.9	0.70*
Within	36	35364.6	982.35	

* Insignificant at level 0.05.

The result in table 1.8 clearly shows that t-value for interactional effect that is the effect between Home environment and Gender came out to 0.70 which is insignificant at 0.05 level. No significant interactional effect of home environment and gender on the adjustment of secondary

school students have been indicated. This means that home environment is impartial with respect to gender.

Educational Implications

Urban school students have better home environment than rural school students. They have better facilities, better options, and their educated parents serve them as better guides, so they are better adjusted than the rural ones. Rural girls usually stay at home. Being more confined to home environment and staying with their parents and bearing household responsibilities at younger age helps them to adjust better as compared to boys who go out play or are engaged in farming on the other hand. Boys and girls in the urban areas have similar exposure and same access to available opportunities. They have equal right to choose and excel in any field, so they are equally adjusted at both home, school or work place. The present study thus reveals that a better and conducive environment should be provided to ensure better adjustment in all spheres of life.

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